

STUDY THE EFFECT OF ANXIETY AND AGGRESSION LEVEL ON PERFORMANCE OF BALL BADMINTON PLAYERS FOR ENHANCING PERFORMANCE

Narendra R. Nikam

Research Scholar, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad

And

Dr. Govind K. Kadam

Professor, Department of Physical Education, Vivekanand Arts & S. D. Com. & Science College, Aurangabad

Abstract:-

The main purpose of the Study the Effect of Anxiety and Aggression level on Performance of Ball Badminton Players for Enhancing Performance of Savitribai Phule Pune University So, the main objective of the present research is to measure the anxiety and aggression of ball badminton players. For the investigation the male and female Ball Badminton Players of various four zones (Pune city, Pune district, Ahmednagar and Nasik) under jurisdiction of Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune aged between 18-25 years are considered as the total sample (N=200) of the study. The research tool for Competitive state Anxiety Inventory-2(CSAI-2) by Martens, Valley & Burton, (1990), Sport Aggression Inventory by Anand Kumar and Prem Shankar Shukla and 't'-test was applied to check the difference between groups. The result obtained through the study showed' at 0.05 level significance.

Aarhat Publication & Aarhat Journals is licensed Based on a work at <http://www.aarhat.com/eiirj/>

Key words: Psychology, Ball Badminton, anxiety and aggression.

Introduction:

The Game of Ball Badminton is wonderful sport are played usually outdoors during the day Ball Badminton is fast paced game demands & requires agility, eye-hand coordination, striking and quick movements and change of direction in quick reflexes of the racquet & yellow ball made by wool. Ball Badminton is requiring quick and good judgment movements to all directions to return the ball to the opponent's side of the court. Ball Badminton is an extremely demanding sport. At an elite level, players are often required top form at their limits of speed, agility, flexibility, endurance and strength. On top of all of this, players must maintain a high state of concentration in order to meet the technical & tactical as well as mental demands of dealing with their opponents. It is therefore essential that everyone involved with the modern game ought to be familiar with the fitness requirements of the game and must know how 'Ball Badminton fitness' can be enhanced.

Competiveness and Anxiety

The increased stress of competitions can cause athletes to react both physically and mentally in a manner that can negatively affect their performance abilities. They may become tense, their heart rates race, they break into a cold sweat, they worry about the outcome of the competition, they find it hard to concentrate on the task in hand. This has led coaches to take an Anxiety is a complex emotional state characterized by a general by tension. It is usually accompanied by tension.

Sports and Aggression

In sport, aggression is a characteristic that can have many negative as well as positive effects on performance. Aggression is defined as “any form of behavior directed toward the goal of harming or injuring another live being who is motivated to avoid such treatment” (Baron & Richardson, 1994). Experienced athletes used self-control to help them with their aggression.

The researcher has therefore undertaken study entitled “To Study the Effect of Anxiety and Aggression level on Performance of Ball Badminton Players for Enhancing Performance of Savitribai Phule Pune University”. In this study the researcher planned to conduct the anxiety and aggression tests on Savitribai Phule Pune university ball badminton players.

Objectives:-

- ❖ To assess the anxiety level of ball badminton players.
- ❖ To assess the aggression level of ball badminton players.
- ❖ To measure the anxiety and aggression of ball badminton players.

Hypothesis:-

H₁: There is significant effect of anxiety level on performance of Ball Badminton Players

H₂: There is significant effect of aggression level on performance of Ball Badminton Players

Variable:-

The Psychological variables are as follows

1. Competitive state Anxiety
2. Sport Aggression

Tools:-

The research tool for Competitive state Anxiety Inventory-2(CSAI-2) by Martens, Valley & Burton, (1990), Sport Aggression Inventory by Anand Kumar and Prem Shankar Shukla

Sample:-

For the investigation the male and female Ball Badminton Players of various four zones (Pune city, Pune district, Ahmednagar and Nasik) under jurisdiction of Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune aged between 18-25 years are considered as the total sample (N=200) of the study.

Statistical Method:-

A statistical technique of 't' test was used to reach the aim of the study.

Result and Discussion:-

It was observed from the Sports Competitive State Anxiety and Aggression variable from table was shows that there was a mean difference between of the sample of 200 cases of Savitribai Phule Pune University, Zones of subjects regarding to the psychological variables.

Table no. 1

Descriptive Statistical of the Sports Competitive State Anxiety Variable for SPPU University, Zone wise Ball Badminton Boys & Girls Players

SPPU Zones	Nasik Zone Ball Badminton Players		Ahmednagar Zone Ball Badminton Players		Pune District Zone Ball Badminton Players		Pune City Zone Ball Badminton Players	
	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls
Variable	Anxiety (CSAI-2)		Anxiety (CSAI-2)		Anxiety (CSAI-2)		Anxiety (CSAI-2)	
Number	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
Mean	60.32	63.08	66.04	68.24	58.16	54.96	53.76	53.88
Std. Error of Mean	0.66	0.46	0.48	0.64	0.51	0.48	0.62	0.36
Median	60.00	63.00	66.00	68.00	58.00	56.00	54.00	54.00
Mode	60.00	62.00	65.00	68.00	58.00	56.00	54.00	54.00
Std. Deviation	3.31	2.34	2.44	3.21	2.57	2.42	3.12	1.83
Variance	10.97	5.49	5.95	10.35	6.64	5.87	9.77	3.36
Skewness	0.127	0.360	-0.237	0.025	0.237	-0.484	-0.221	-0.205
Std. Error of Skewness	0.464	0.446	0.464	0.464	0.446	0.464	0.464	0.446
Kurtosis	-1.200	0.711	-0.359	0.754	-0.042	-0.629	-0.826	-1.023
Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.902	0.902	0.902	0.902	0.902	0.902	0.902	0.902

The data of Sports Competitive State Anxiety variable as shown in Table 4.1 reveals that mean, standard deviation, skewness & kurtosis value of the distribution of Sports Competitive State Anxiety of the sample of 200 cases of Savitribai Phule Pune University, Zones. Nashik Zone 25 Ball Badminton Boys players mean value of Sports Competitive State Anxiety 60.32, SD 3.31, skewness & kurtosis value 0.127 & -1.200. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Nashik Zone Ball Badminton boys Sports Competitive State Anxiety in the present study is mostly normal. & Nashik Zone 25 Ball Badminton Girls players mean value of Sports Competitive State Anxiety 63.08, SD 2.34, skewness & kurtosis value 0.360 & 0.711. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Nashik Zone Ball Badminton girls Sports Competitive State Anxiety in the present study is nearly normal.

Ahmednagar Zone 25 Ball Badminton Boys players mean value of Sports Competitive State Anxiety 66.04, SD 2.44, skewness & kurtosis value -0.237 & -0.359. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Ahmednagar Zone Ball Badminton boys Sports Competitive State Anxiety in the present study is mostly normal. & Ahmednagar Zone 25 Ball Badminton Girls players mean value of Sports Competitive State Anxiety 68.24, SD 3.21, skewness & kurtosis value 0.025 & 0.754. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Ahmednagar Zone Ball Badminton girls Sports Competitive State Anxiety in the present study is nearly normal.

Pune District Zone 25 Ball Badminton Boys players mean value of Sports Competitive State Anxiety 58.16, SD 2.57, skewness & kurtosis value 0.237 & -0.042. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Pune District Zone Ball Badminton boys Sports Competitive State Anxiety in the present study is mostly normal. & Pune District Zone 25 Ball Badminton Girls players mean value of Sports Competitive State Anxiety 54.96, SD 2.42, skewness & kurtosis value -0.484 & -0.629. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Pune District Zone Ball Badminton girls Sports Competitive State Anxiety in the present study is mostly normal.

Pune City Zone 25 Ball Badminton Boys players mean value of Sports Competitive State Anxiety 53.76, SD 3.12, skewness & kurtosis value -0.221 & -0.826. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Pune City Zone Ball Badminton boys Sports Competitive State Anxiety in the present study is mostly normal. & Pune City Zone 25 Ball Badminton Girls players mean value of Sports Competitive State Anxiety 53.88, SD 1.83, skewness & kurtosis value -0.205 & -1.023. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Pune City Zone Ball Badminton girls Sports Competitive State Anxiety in the present study is mostly normal.

Table no. 2

**Descriptive Statistical of the Aggression Variable for
SPPU University, Zone wise Ball Badminton Boys & Girls Players**

SPPU Zones	Nashik Zone Ball Badminton Players		Ahmednagar Zone Ball Badminton Players		Pune District Zone Ball Badminton Players		Pune City Zone Ball Badminton Players	
	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls
Variable	Aggression		Aggression		Aggression		Aggression	
Number	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
Mean	13.96	12.72	13.92	12.88	16.76	15.08	17.56	16.76
Std. Error of Mean	0.22	0.17	0.23	0.18	0.18	0.25	0.17	0.19
Median	14.00	13.00	14.00	13.00	17.00	15.00	18.00	17.00
Mode	14.00	13.00	14.00	13.00	17.00	15.00	18.00	17.00
Std. Deviation	1.13	0.89	1.15	0.92	0.92	1.28	0.86	0.96
Variance	1.29	0.79	1.32	0.86	0.85	1.66	0.75	0.94
Skewness	-0.101	-0.158	-0.010	0.254	-0.163	0.221	-0.199	0.228
Std. Error of Skewness	0.464	0.446	0.464	0.464	0.446	0.464	0.464	0.446
Kurtosis	-0.515	-0.597	-0.658	-0.132	-0.784	-0.169	-0.436	0.009
Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.902	0.902	0.902	0.902	0.902	0.902	0.902	0.902

The data of Aggression variable as shown in Table 4.2 reveals that mean, standard deviation, skewness & kurtosis value of the distribution of Aggression of the sample of 200 cases of Savitribai Phule Pune University, Zones. Nashik Zone 25 Ball Badminton Boys players mean value of Aggression 13.96, SD 1.13, skewness & kurtosis value -0.101 & -0.515. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Nashik Zone Ball Badminton boys Aggression in the present study is mostly normal. & Nashik Zone 25 Ball Badminton Girls players mean value of Aggression 12.72, SD 0.89, skewness & kurtosis value -0.158 & -0.597. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Nashik Zone Ball Badminton girls Aggression in the present study is mostly normal.

Ahmednagar Zone 25 Ball Badminton Boys players mean value of Aggression 13.92, SD 1.15, skewness & kurtosis value -0.010 & -0.658. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Ahmednagar Zone Ball Badminton boys Aggression in the present study is mostly normal. & Ahmednagar Zone 25 Ball Badminton Girls players mean value of Aggression 12.88, SD 0.92, skewness & kurtosis value 0.254 & -0.132. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Ahmednagar Zone Ball Badminton girls Aggression in the present study is mostly normal.

Pune District Zone 25 Ball Badminton Boys players mean value of Aggression 16.76, SD 0.92, skewness & kurtosis value -0.163 & -0.784. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Pune District Zone Ball Badminton boys Aggression in the present study is mostly normal. & Pune District Zone 25 Ball Badminton Girls players mean value of Aggression 15.08, SD 1.28, skewness & kurtosis value 0.221 & -0.169. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Pune District Zone Ball Badminton girls Aggression in the present study is mostly normal.

Pune City Zone 25 Ball Badminton Boys players mean value of Aggression 17.56, SD 0.86, skewness & kurtosis value -0.199 & -0.436. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Pune City Zone Ball Badminton boys Aggression in the present study is mostly normal. & Pune City Zone 25 Ball Badminton Girls players mean value of Aggression 16.76, SD 0.96, skewness & kurtosis value 0.228 & 0.009 It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Pune City Zone Ball Badminton girls Aggression in the present study is nearly normal.

It was that Anxiety & Aggression are highly related to better performance in sports & games. Anxiety & Aggression contribute to enhance and down the sports & games performance.

Graph no. 1

**Sports Competitive State Anxiety Mean value for
SPPU University, Zone wise Ball Badminton Boys & Girls Players**

Graph no. 2

Aggression Mean value for SPPU University, Zone wise
Ball Badminton Boys & Girls Players

Graphical representation of Graph one and two Sports Competitive State Anxiety And Aggression Mean score data of Aggression variable as shown reveals that mean, standard deviation value of the distribution of Aggression of the sample of 200 cases of Savitribai Phule Pune University, Zones.

Discussion

Discussion of the results of sports competitive state anxiety & aggression inventories consist which indicate the level of anxiety and aggression of Savitribai Phule Pune University, Nashik, Ahmednagar, Pune District & Pune City Zone wise selected Ball Badminton boys and girls players as:

It was observed from the findings that the to study the effect of Anxiety & Aggression level on performance of Savitribai Phule Pune University. In the result of study from table no. 1 & 2 shown that there was Nashik Zone Ball Badminton boys & girls players level of sports competitive state anxiety was high & similar players level of aggression was low, Ahmednagar Zone Ball Badminton boys & girls players level of sports competitive state anxiety was high & similar players level of aggression was low, Pune District Zone Ball Badminton boys & girls players level of sports competitive state anxiety was low & similar players level of aggression was high and Pune City Zone Ball Badminton boys & girls players level of sports competitive state anxiety was low & similar players level of aggression was high.

Conclusion:

It was concluded that important in view of the Anxiety & Aggression in Ball Badminton Boys & Girls players of Savitribai Phule Pune University, Nashik, Ahmednagar, Pune District & Pune City Zone. Concluded that researcher evidence revealed the level of Anxiety & Aggression in Ball Badminton Boys & Girls players these Psychological variables are vital in the field of sports coaching and performance. It is known from the review of related literature that status to level of Anxiety & Aggression of sports players. It was concluded that study may help to developed efficient coaching plan for better performance consider the Anxiety & Aggression variables of the psychology.

References :

- Ajmer Singh, Jagdish Bains, J. S. Gill, R. S. Brar & N. Rathee (2004).** Essential of Physical Education, New Delhi: Xpress Graphics.
- Alegaokar P.M. (1997):** Sports psychology, Pune: Pune vidyarthi Griha Prakashan
- Austin, S., Graham, J. (1993):** Intensity and Frequency dimension of Comparative State Anxiety, Retrieved, Jan 2nd, 2011, from Journal of Sports Science, Web Site: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>
- Beauchmp, M. R., Bray, S.R., Eys, M.A., Carron, A.V. (2003):** The Effect of Role Ambiguity on Competitive State Anxiety, Retrieved, Jan 2nd, 2011, from Journal of Sports Psychology, Vol. 25 P.72-92 Website: <http://www.cabdirect.org>